

NOTES

Rhodium(I) and Rhodium(III) Complexes of 1-Amidino-2-thioureas

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1-AMIDINO-2-thiourea(HATU), *N*-methyl-1-amidino-2-thiourea(HNMATU) and *S*-alkyl-1-amidino-2-thiourea(HSMATU) form a large number of complexes with metal ions in which they functions as NN and SN donors depending upon the conditions¹. In the SN donor mode they stabilise lower oxidation states of the metals. In this communication, the complexes of Rh^I and Rh^{III} with these ligands have been studied with a view to find out the bonding pattern of the ligands.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Preparation of complexes :

[Rh^{III}(ATU)₂Cl]₂ and [Rh^{III}(NMATU)₂Cl]₂ : To a methanolic solution (25 ml) of RhCl₃·3H₂O (0.01 mmol) was added respective ligand solution (0.03 mmol) in methanol. The yellow product obtained immediately was filtered, washed several time with methanol and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride vacuum desiccator. The compounds were stable for atleast one year.

[Rh^I(HATU)(TPP)Cl] and [Rh^I(HNMATU)(TPP)Cl] : The complexes were prepared from [Rh(TPP)₃Cl]³⁺. To [Rh(TPP)₃Cl]³⁺ (0.01 mmol, TPP=triphenylphosphine) in acetone (25 ml), a solution (25 ml) of respective ligand in methanol was added. The mixture was stirred at 10° and gradually the maroon coloured substance went into solution. It was filtered and the filtrate was kept in a desiccator for slow evaporation. The resulting yellow crystalline solid was filtered and dried over calcium chloride vacuum desiccator. The compounds were stable for atleast one year. Analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Ir (KBr and mull), electronic and pmr spectra were taken respectively on Perkin-Elmer Infrared 625, Cary 17D and EM 390 90 MMz Spectrophotometers. Magnetic and conductance measurement were carried out on a Gouy balance and a Philips conductivity bridge respectively.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF Rh^I AND Rh^{III} COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
	Rh	N	S	Cl
[Rh(ATU) ₂ Cl] ₂	27.79 (27.68)	30.25 (30.10)	17.02 (17.20)	9.72 (9.54)
[Rh(NMATU) ₂ Cl] ₂	24.65 (24.82)	26.82 (27.00)	15.65 (15.42)	8.72 (8.55)
[Rh(HATU)(TPP)Cl]	19.75 (19.98)	10.98 (10.83)	6.52 (6.88)	6.95 (6.86)
[Rh(HNMATU)(TPP)Cl]	19.50 (19.36)	10.39 (10.53)	6.21 (6.02)	6.85 (6.67)

Results and Discussion

Both rhodium(I) (orange yellow) and rhodium(III) (brownish yellow) complexes are insoluble in aqueous and common organic solvents, but soluble in DMSO. Low molar conductance of the complexes shows their non-ionic character. Both compounds are diamagnetic which is most likely for both 4d⁶ and 4d⁸ system particularly for 4d transition metal ions². The ligands are deprotonated in case of the Rh^{III} complexes wheseas they are neutral in the Rh^I complexes. From the comparison of infrared spectra of the complexes with those of ligands, it is found that the band due to ν_{N-C-S}(1), ν_{N-C-S}(2), ν_{N-C-S}(3) and ν_{C-S} show a blue-shift in the complexes. Again, the two bands at ~530 and ~330 cm⁻¹ in the complexes are not observed in the ligands.

All these proved that the ligands are bonded with metals through S and N donor atoms. The band appearing at ~2 240 cm⁻¹ for the Rh^{III} complexes is most probably due to SH.

The electronic spectra (DMSO) of the Rh^{III} complexes do not give any band except a shoulder at ~670 nm. The base line started rising from the beginning. Although two bands are expected for the Rh^{III} complexes³, these bands are probably masked by the CT bands in this case. Two bands appeared in case of the Rh^I complexes at ~18 000 and ~25 000 cm⁻¹. The band at ~18 000 cm⁻¹ has a very low intensity (ε=50) while that at ~25 000 cm⁻¹ has ε=2 500 mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Square-planar Rh^I complexes are characterised⁴ by its band in the region 25 000–28 000 cm⁻¹. This band is assigned to charge transfer transition from the filled metal 4d_{z²} orbital to empty ligand *n*-orbital.

The pmr spectral band assignments of the complexes have been made with reference to [Ni(Hbg)₂Cl]₂⁵. The pmr spectra of [Rh(ATU)₂Cl]₂ show a broad signal at τ 5.9 while [Rh(NMATU)₂Cl]₂ shows two signals at τ 7.3 (due to CH₃) and 6.2 (Hβ₁+Hβ₂). These are in the intensity ratio of 3 : 3. The signal due to proton

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atom attached to S-atom was not observed probably due to its presence in the negative region. [Rh(HATU)(TPP)Cl] gives signals at τ 6.3 ($H\beta_1 + H\beta_2$), 5.4 (H_α), 2.7 (phenyl proton) and 0.91 (H_γ) in the intensity ratio of 4 : 1 : 15 : 1. For [Rh(HNMATU)(TPP)Cl], the signals are at τ 7.3 (CH_3), 7.0 (H_α), 6.0 ($H\beta_1 + H\beta_2$), 2.7 (phenyl) and 1 (H_γ), having the intensity ratio of 3 : 1 : 3 : 15 : 1. The appearance of these signals indicates the presence of a strong ring-current in the metal chelate ring.

From the above discussion it is concluded that Rh^{III} forms SN bonded octahedral complexes while Rh^I forms square-planar complexes with the ligands and TPP.

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The Thermodynamic Dissociation Constant of $MgSO_4$ in 10% Dioxane - Water Solution at 308.15 K

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A study of the thermodynamics of dissociation of the sulphates of bivalent metals in aquo-organic media requires the determination of the dissociation constant of the sulphates at a number of temperatures.

Dissociation constant (K) of $MgSO_4$ in dioxane - water mixed solvent of various dioxane content has been determined by Mason and Shutt¹ at 293.15 K from dielectric constant measurements. Dunsmore and James² determined K at 298.15 K in 10 and 20% dioxane content of dioxane - water mixed solvent from conductivity measurements.

These values of K are likely to be less accurate than the values obtained from e m f. measurements with cells having no liquid junction potential which is now established to give the most accurate values

for the dissociation constant of electrolytes. Hence both cells (C-1) and (C-2) were set up.

Experimental

H_2SO_4 , $MgSO_4$ and HCl used were all of G.R. grade. Three stock solutions of $MgSO_4$ and H_2SO_4 in water in molal ratio 5 : 1, 3 : 1 and 1 : 1 respectively and another stock solution of $MgSO_4$ and HCl in equimolar proportion were prepared. These were then appropriately mixed with water and then dioxane to prepare solutions of known molality in 10% (w/w) dioxane of the mixed solvent. The solutions were deoxygenated and filled in cells as described previously. The setting up of the all-glass cell, thermostat, e m f. assembly etc were as described earlier³. The cells came to equilibrium quickly but e.m.f. readings were taken after 2 h of the introduction of the cells in the thermostat, at intervals of 0.5 h for at least 1.5 h over which the e.m.f. readings of the duplicate cells remained constant within 0.02 mV. The mean of the two e.m.f. readings after correcting for barometric pressure, vapour pressure and bubbler depth was recorded.

Results and Discussion

The e.m.f. of cell (C-1) is given by equation (1),

$$E = E^0 - \frac{k}{2} \log m_H^2 m_{SO_4} \nu_H^2 \nu_{SO_4} \quad (1)$$

which reduces to equation (2) since it has been established that modified Davies equation is valid in this case⁴.

$$E = E^0 - \frac{k}{2} \log m_H^2 m_{SO_4} + \frac{3k A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - \frac{k}{2} \beta_1 \mu \quad (2)$$

where, $k = 2.3026 RT/F$, A = appropriate Debye-Hückel constant, and $\beta_1 = 2\beta_H + \beta_{SO_4}$.

If we assume that Hg_2SO_4 is completely dissociated then Scheme 1 should represent the equilibria present in the solution of cell (C-1) and equations (3), (4) and (5) should hold.

Scheme 1